

MUSE: a Music-making Sandbox Environment for Real-Time Collaborative Play

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports the concept, design, and prototyping of *MUSE*, a real-time, turn based, collaborative music making application for users with little to no formal music education background. *MUSE* (a Music Sandbox Experience) is a proof-of-concept, web application running exclusively in the *Chrome* web browser for four players using gamepad controllers. First, we outline the proposed methodology with respect to related research and discuss our approach to designing *MUSE* through a partial gamification of music using a player-centric design framework. Second, we explain the implementation and prototyping of *MUSE*. Third, we highlight recent observations of participants using our proof-of-concept application during a short art/installation gallery exhibition. In conclusion, we reflect on our design methodology based on the informal user feedback we received and look at several approaches into improving *MUSE*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Computer-mediated, real-time collaborative music applications and interfaces could be categorized as either *serious musical instruments* or *playful musical toys*.

Serious musical instrument applications and interfaces provide their users the means to produce a quality, original music content in real-time. They usually feature an increased human-computer interaction complexity due to the large amount of musical controls they offer. This characteristic gives their users extensive creative freedom and the opportunity for skill mastery which in return leads to long-term engagement with the instrument. However, the quality of both the interaction and the musical result is directly related to the amount of time and effort invested by each user in mastering the required individual skills as well as acquiring collaborative experience as a musical ensemble. Moreover, the approach taken in designing most of these instruments relies on a substantial amount of either traditional or genre specific music notation, terminology, and/or concepts. Users lacking this knowledge will often

create unsatisfactory, poor quality musical content resulting in a loss of interest in using that particular collaborative application or interface.

Musical toys on the other hand, don't require any musical education knowledge or group playing experience in order to interact with them successfully. These applications usually abstract most of the musical concepts they implement by presenting users with a small number of simple, intuitive controls. Apart from making the learning process easy, musical toys often produce a musical output of a consistent, pleasant quality, regardless of their users' individual or group proficiency. By making their users feel musically "competent" in virtually no time, applications and interfaces in this category appeal to large demographics. However, even when they do present some skill mastery opportunities (e.g. eye-hand coordination), musical toys often do not allow users to produce original content and express their musical creativity.

The main characteristics of these two categories place them at rather opposite ends of what appears to be a continuous spectrum. We felt that there was a potential middle-ground area worth exploring found between a *serious musical instrument* and a *playful musical toy*. The challenge was to merge two seemingly contrasting attributes: (1) the ease of use of a musical toy and (2) the interaction depth that allows for creative expression usually found in a musical instrument. The resulting application would therefore have to provide users with easy-to-grasp functionality and controls while allowing for producing original, pleasant musical results in a collaborative setting.

2. RELATED WORK

The initial goal of this research project was to provide users with little to no musical education background a platform for creating collaborative music in real-time. Primarily, we focused on addressing central issues found in a number of co-operative music-making applications and interfaces: (1) a lack of creative freedom found in many commercial games that we consider *musical toys*, such as *RockBand*TM, *GuitarHero*TM [1] or *Rocksmith*TM [2], and (2) Real-time musical output of inconsistent quality identified in academic research projects approaching collaborative music-making from a *serious musical instrument* perspective [3, 4].

Mainstream co-operative music games favor eye-hand coordination skill over the musical creative freedom of

their users; players usually have to match visual cues they receive on screen with the hand / finger position on the input device they control [1]. The success of these types of music games for broad audiences is based on two main design choices: first, they use prerecorded hit-songs which ensure a recognizable, engaging, and ultimately satisfactory musical output every time they are played, and second, they are easy to learn and use. The long-term engagement of players with these games does not stem from a creative pool of musical curiosity but from the ongoing challenge/reward system for successful coordination of player input with visual cues in real time. From a music creativity perspective these games do not offer any real musical choice to the player. All interaction happens at the gameplay, non-musical level only. *Rocksmith*TM uses a real electric guitar as input device and tracks the player's input proficiency against a predetermined musical score. The overall music is comprised of a pre-recorded mix of a hit-song with the player's instrument track muted; in this case the player produces his own sounds in real-time and is rewarded as long as he correctly plays his part according to the score. The game thus expands more into the *serious musical instrument* territory by providing an opportunity for mastery leading to long-term engagement usually associated with traditional musical instruments. However, just like in *RockBand* or *GuitarHero*, the player's creativity is entirely restricted due to a lack of access to creating original music output [2]. Although several players can play as a group, since the design of these games disregards creative choice, the possibility for collaborative inspiration and creativity to occur is non-existent.

Unlike commercial games, a number of academic projects addressing real-time collaborative music such as *TOUCHtr4ck* [3] and *The Music Pattern* [4] use a *serious musical instrument* approach in designing their interfaces. They focus more on musical creativity and long-term engagement but somehow overlook the importance of setting limits to the users' level of creative input in their design choice [5]. We found that by giving users control to a large amount of musical parameters without taking a structured approach to the design of the system, these applications often produce real-time musical results of questionable quality, especially when used by people with no music education background.

*reacTable*TM [6], a tangible interface using a modular synthesizer approach designed for producing live electronic dance music, managed to significantly increase the overall quality of the ongoing musical output by narrowing down to a specific musical genre, *electronica*. *reacTable* allows one or more users to freely control pre-determined musical loops and sound parameters represented by physical objects placed onto a tangible tabletop display. The interface provides users with a clear visual feedback of the individual music objects' state and of the overall music system status at any time that leads to an engaging human-computer interaction. Since it features a considerable amount of musical and sound parameter controls, *reacTable* belongs mostly to the *serious musical instrument* category. Due to the high degree of creative freedom it offers, in the case of a multi-user setup, the actions of one player directly influence the other players' musical

choices, thus greatly enhancing the collaborative experience. However, the ease of use of a *musical toy* is compromised due to the heavy reliance on electronic music concepts, such as modular synthesis music making techniques and its associated graphic symbols and metaphors. Because *reacTable* was designed primarily as a solo musical instrument for DJs, the quality of the overall music output is directly impacted by the users' knowledge and mastery of the afore-mentioned techniques and their group playing experience.

3. CONCEPT

Following the findings presented above, and based on our proposition that there is potential for merging collaborative *musical toys* with *serious instruments*, we set some preliminary design goals for our interface, in that it should: (1) produce an overall pleasant musical output, (2) allow users to express their musical creativity without relying on any music education or experience prerequisites, (3) provide users with an easy-to-use interface, and (4) offer users the opportunity for mastering musical skills leading to long-term engagement with the interface. Overall, we envisioned a co-located, real-time gameplay where the contribution of one player would change the ongoing musical output to a certain degree, which in return would act as a creative stimulus for the musical choices of the other players.

Based on our literature review we concluded that providing novice users with an increased level of musical controls while presenting them with a non-structured musical environment usually leads to inconsistent and sometimes unsatisfactory musical results. Since our first design requirement was to produce "an overall pleasant musical output" we set on designing a system capable of producing a consistent, pleasurable sound output with no sudden drops in the quality of the music. Although we wanted to offer increased creative freedom to our users compared to other collaborative *musical toys*, we believe that what leads to the players' long-term engagement with an interface is not the mere presence of countless affordances [7] but that of a system of rules in which those affordances co-exist. This system of rules is what differentiates playing with toys (*paidia*) from playing games (*ludus*). Whereas *paidia* relates to spontaneity, excitement, and improvisation, *ludus* refers to rule-based, system-defined, organized play [8]. The long-term engagement found in rule based games resides in the vast amount of possibilities within the boundaries of the game. Similarly, by defining a clear set of rules, a *musical toy* can be elevated to the *playful platform for serious play* status, or simply put, a *game of music*.

4. DESIGN FRAMEWORK

From a design perspective, games can be either games of *progression* or *emergence* [9]. In a game of *progression* the designer has absolute control of the game's flow of events and challenges. This is achieved through carefully scripted level design. Games of progression are a good approach to designing narrative-driven computer games. However, replayability is usually very low due to the

scripted flow of the game combined with a limited amount of player options, and that of an already known outcome of the game on subsequent plays. Our interest was to approach *MUSE* as a game of *emergence*, as most rule-based games fall under this category and since we wanted *MUSE* to be played in real-time. In a game of emergence, the game state is continuously and directly influenced by the interactions between players with the game rules and components. Even a small set of relatively simple rules can lead to a vast number of possible states the game can be in at a given time. Games of emergence have a considerable replay value due to the high probability space they offer. Following our hypothesis that a *musical toy* governed by a small set of gameplay rules may result in a game of musical emergence, we approached *gamification* as a suitable solution to designing *MUSE*.

4.1 Gamification of Music

Gamification is the process through which game design elements are implemented in non-game contexts [10]. Gamification aims to increase user activity, quality of experience, and social interaction by adding a layer of gamefulness to a given design. We considered two approaches in gamifying *MUSE*: *complete gamification* – translating an existing tabletop or computer game system into the music domain, and *partial gamification* – implementing discrete game mechanics¹ by matching them with particular music concepts, controls, or parameters.

4.1.1 Complete Gamification - hypothesis

Since most board games and many computer games are games of emergence, we initially approached the gamification of *MUSE* by looking at translating an existing tabletop or computer game system into the music domain. After paper-prototyping some ideas, we realized that a successful integration of a complete game system with music – hence of a unified, coherent set of several game mechanics – may fail due to a number of issues we discuss here.

Within a given game system, the choice of actions does undeniably elicit an emotional response in the player, and their intensity fluctuates in direct relation with the impact a particular action has on the internal economy of the game world. For instance, in a game of *Chess*, the less decisive opening moves have less impact on the outcome of the game – thus producing less intense emotional response in players – compared to the game-changing, tension filled middle-game moves. In the same way, actions executed while performing music elicit a vast range of emotional responses in players based on many factors such as the setting of the performance, musical context, overall disposition of the participants, the specific role each player has in the ensemble, and many others.

All the possible interactions a player can have with an artifact – also called *motivational affordances* [12] – are the perceived opportunities that lead to a rewarding game experience, as perceived by the player in relationship with the game. It follows that the internal economy of a game system shapes the motivational affordances out of which

the players' intrinsic motivation stems. We can then conclude that motivational affordances and the user satisfaction they convey cannot exist outside the internal economy of the system that generates them.

From a theoretical standpoint, a matching of the economics of the game system with the economics of real-time collaborative music is required in order to preserve the motivational affordances responsible for generating engaging, emergent gameplay. Even if this approach proves effective, the translation of the time domain from one system to another would pose a significant design challenge. The passing of time, as dictated by game rules, can render a game system either “fun” to play, where players enter a state of psychological “flow” [13], or turn it into a completely tedious activity. The timing of what is perceived as good “flow” in a particular tabletop game may negatively impact the creation and perception of real-time music. We therefore concluded that a successful translation of a complete game system into the music domain was not feasible due to the unique idiosyncrasies of these two mediums.

4.1.2 Partial Gamification of *MUSE*

We implemented several discrete game mechanics into the real-time music-making domain. A few of the game rules, interface, and game elements we tested revealed novel and interesting ways of interacting with music. However, the vast majority of the mechanics lost their gameplay effectiveness when translated into music. This finding confirmed Deterding's view on gamification [14] that game elements that are successful within a game system do not necessarily maintain their attributes when translated to a new context. He suggests that designers should conceptualize these perceived opportunities as *situated motivational affordances*, in that they are both *artificial* – object specific – and *situational* – context or system specific. It became obvious to us that grouping a number of successful but discrete game mechanics together will not result in a coherent, logical real-time music system. Consequently, we focused on the overall quality of the system we wanted to produce instead of trying to build a unified system out of disconnected mechanics.

The approach we took into designing *MUSE* is based on the *MDA* model as described by Hunicke [15]. *MDA* – *mechanics-dynamics-aesthetics* – is a game development model which takes a player-centric, top-down approach to the design process. Instead of starting with the game mechanics to be implemented in the design (feature-driven) the focus is instead shifted towards the player's experience (aesthetics-driven). The usual steps of action are: (1) identifying the aesthetics the designer hopes to achieve, (2) defining the dynamics that may lead to those game experiences, and (3) creating the mechanics that produce the envisioned dynamics. In other words, we established the desirable emotional responses we wanted players to experience upon interacting with the game, we looked at what the game system's behavior should be at run-time based on the player's input, and lastly, we identified the game

¹ Game mechanics are comprised of game rules, interface, and game components [11].

components, interface, and rules necessary for the specified dynamics to emerge. *MUSE*'s overall aesthetic goal was to provide inexperienced users with a pleasurable, engaging musical experience in a collaborative setting in real-time. The emotional response we were most interested in can be also referred to as plain "fun", but the term lacks specificity. Hunicke [15] proposes a relatively broad taxonomy containing eight categories of emotions (Table 3) usually experienced by users while playing games.

We decided that *MUSE*'s proof-of-concept main aesthetics should incorporate *Sensation*, *Expression*, and *Submission* (in this particular order of importance). If the proof-of-concept proved feasible, secondary aesthetics could include *Discovery*, *Fellowship*, and *Challenge*. The game dynamics generating these emotions thus had to first: produce real-time pleasant musical output (game as sense-pleasure), second: provide users access to musical self-expression (game as self-discovery), and third: allow for a curiosity-driven, unrushed exploration of musical possibilities in real-time (game as pastime).

Sensation Game as sense-pleasure	Fantasy Game as make-believe
Narrative Game as unfolding story	Challenge Game as obstacle course
Fellowship Game as social framework	Discovery Game as uncharted territory
Expression Game as self-discovery	Submission Game as pastime

Table 3. Hunicke's eight categories of emotions experienced during play, part of the MDA design framework.

The last step in outlining *MUSE*'s design structure was to identify the mechanics (components, interface, and game rules) that allow for the desired dynamics to take place. Several preliminary mechanics were considered as a direct result of the dynamics presented above: (1) limiting players' access to low-level musical controls such as individual pitches, velocities, etc. in order to ensure a pleasant overall sound output and minimize downtime, (2) abstracting musical concepts into easy-to-grasp interface elements with intuitive controls, and (3) creating an open-ended, sandbox music environment with no incentives other than musical ones (see Table 4).

<i>Desired Dynamic</i>	<i>Design Approach</i>
Produce real-time pleasant musical output	Limit the users' access to low-level musical controls
Provide access to musical self-expression	Abstract musical concepts into easy-to-grasp interface
Allow for ongoing exploration of musical possibilities in real-time	Create an open-ended, sandbox environment based on musical incentives only

Table 4. The design approaches leading to the desired game dynamics in *MUSE* (based on the MDA approach)

In designing *MUSE* we aimed at producing a music-output continuum ranging from *non-disturbing – interesting* to *pleasant – exciting* musical qualities. Although prone to subjective interpretation and in significant need of user testing, we assessed the quality of the music output in regards to our target audience. In terms of musical genre, we decided to gravitate around a combination of minimalistic [16] and popular music within a western music tradition context. A similar project, *Polymetros* [17], had used a minimalistic music approach and received a good audience response with regards to the musical genre. Within these musical boundaries, we approached designing *MUSE* focusing on maximizing the quality of the musical output of the system towards the *pleasant - exciting* end of the spectrum for most of the playing time.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

Based on the design choices outlined in Table 4 we implemented the game's interface, components, and mechanics (game rules) as presented below. After creating a number of musical game components and controls and testing them on several different game-board layouts, we realized that the amount of low-level user control still had to be significantly reduced for the following reasons: 1. the more fine control we had as designers over the "no-wrong-notes" system, the better the musical quality of the overall sound output, resulting in an enjoyable gameplay, and 2. in a real-time musical environment, small, low-impact musical actions/changes do not carry enough emotional response in the user to be worthwhile for novice players to perform. These fine alterations can only produce interesting musical results when handled by proficient musicians only; even then, since these changes are musically low-impact, they need to happen quickly and quite often to be musically effective.

We chose to design a very simple graphical interface, with no visual clutter, to allow users to grasp the connection between the overall music output and the visual representation of the music system at any time. The input control uses all gamepad buttons except the two 2-axis analog joysticks. For intuitive interaction and consistent control, colored gamepad buttons – Y X, A, and B – control graphic elements of the same color in the game.

In terms of duration of play, being in the proof-of-concept stage, *MUSE* is now completely open-ended, with no time limitation imposed by the gameplay. There are no points given to the players or any other reward systems in place, since we wanted to observe users' interactions within the game's controlled environment and quantify the emotional responses elicited in players based only on their musical actions, interactions, preferences, and perceptions. These observations could potentially lead to establishing a *musical hierarchy of motivational affordances* within *MUSE*. This could be later used as foundation for implementing more complex game mechanics leading to higher levels of interaction based on the intensity hierarchy of these responses.

5.1 MUSE's System Description

The sound output of *MUSE* is comprised of four distinct 8-note loops that play continuously throughout the game session. Each player is assigned a musical loop of eight repeated notes at the beginning of the game. Each loop uses a distinct musical timbre (instrument) for the entire duration of the game. The sound banks of the loops were sampled from a digital synthesizer and span eight octaves in range. They are asynchronously loaded [18] into the web browser's cache memory during web page loading. For *MUSE*'s proof-of-concept sound banks we sampled two plucked string instruments and two pitched percussion sounds. To lower the memory load on the browser and to increase the timbral color based on the sample's velocity, we recorded one stereo sample (16bit / 44100Hz) at three distinct velocity levels – soft, medium, and loud corresponding to fixed MIDI velocity values – for every octave. All intermediate notes are transposed at run time in *MUSE*. Each sound bank thus holds one sample times eight octaves times three velocity layers to get 24 samples.

5.2 Graphical User Interface

MUSE is comprised of an eight by eight grid in which rows correspond to octaves and columns to speeds. Each player's loop can occupy one tile of the grid at any given time. The position on the grid affects the range (octave) and the playing speed of the loop. Every row corresponds to a different octave with loops sounding higher if positioned high on the grid. The speed distribution ranges from very slow on the left of grid to very fast to the right, with loops doubling or halving their speed depending on their position on the grid (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The eight speeds by eight ranges grid in *MUSE*

5.3 Game Components

A geometric shape represents a player's musical loop within the game. The player's name is displayed in the top-left corner of the tile. This representation of the loop is referred to as a *BLOCK* in the game (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. A player's *BLOCK* in *MUSE*.

The starting shape for all players is the *SQUARE*. This shape is the graphical representation of an eight note loop playing the same pitch at one fixed velocity. Other shapes available throughout the game are: *TRIANGLE* – same pitch, various velocities, *CIRCLE* – various pitches, same velocity, and *PENTAGON* – various pitches and velocities. All pitch/velocity contours are randomly generated during gameplay. Because the shapes' pitch/velocity complexity increases from *SQUARE* to *PENTAGON*, in order to further control the quality of the musical output we limited the amount of shapes available in the game as follows: maximum four *SQUARES*, three *TRIANGLES*, two *CIRCLES*, and one *PENTAGON*.

Figure 3. The graphic representation of all the available pitch/velocity contours in *MUSE*

5.4 Gameplay

Each player is automatically positioned on a tile close to the middle of the grid at the start of the game. Users begin playing by taking turns in activating (turning ON) their loops / *BLOCKS*. Since we wanted users to easily grasp the relationships between their actions and the musical results they produced, we implemented the turn-taking game mechanic in *MUSE*. Turn taking also allows a player to see what other players' musical contributions and preferences are, clearly hear the musical result produced, thus learning through observation [19]. Each player has a time counter displayed at the top-right corner of their *BLOCK* (see Figure 2) and receives 25 seconds of time each turn, time they can use on their turn to perform a game action of their choice. Once the timer reaches zero, the active player's turn ends immediately. If a player wishes to have more than 25 seconds available on their turn, they can *End Turn* before the timer runs out. Since they receive 25 seconds each turn, if players wish they can *End Turn* several times and accumulate up to a maximum of 60 seconds of available time.

On their turn, players can choose to either perform an action affecting only their own *BLOCK* or actions controlling all players' *BLOCKS*. The actions available for their own *BLOCK* are: (1) *Move Block*: allows players to move their *BLOCK* on the grid, thus changing their loop's register and speed in real time, (2) *Change Shape* which instantly changes the melodic / rhythmic contour of their *BLOCK* as per the geometrical shapes' musical characteristics described in section 5.3, and (3) *End Turn* which allows the current player to carry over to the next turn the

amount of unused time. The *End Turn* action passes the turn to the next player in the game.

The actions controlling all players' *BLOCKS* are: (1) *Move All Blocks*: similar to *Move Block* but moving all players on the grid, (2) *Refresh Blocks*: this action randomly generates new melodic / rhythmic contours for the current shapes in the game, (3) *Swap Blocks*: randomly swapping either the position of all the *BLOCKS* on the grid or the *SHAPES* among the players, (4) *Play Blocks*: allows users to perform a real-time chord progression for the entire musical output, and (5) *End Turn*: identical with the one presented above.

A special condition applies to the players' movement on the grid: if an active player moves their *BLOCK* onto a tile occupied by a passive player, the passive player is temporarily removed from the *GRID* and their loop sound is muted. An active player can thus remove all other players from the game for a significant musical change. Removed players take turns as usual having the following options: (1) *Get Back*: allows them to select any tile on the grid and re-enter the game (placing their *BLOCK* on the grid and activating the loop's sound – mute OFF) and (2) *End Turn*: as described above. The time needed for a removed player to get back on the grid is not accounted for. Upon re-entering the game the player has access to the usual (i.e. timed) game actions: *My Block* or *All Blocks*.

When moving on the grid, players can continuously move in any direction, since the *GRID* is designed so that loops/*BLOCKS* can "circle" through either octaves or speeds. In other words, a player's *BLOCK* located on the top row (highest sounding register) can still move up, resulting in the *BLOCK* being placed on the bottom row of the same column (lowest register). The same approach applies to speeds. Figure 4 shows a gameplay screenshot of *MUSE*.

Figure 4. Screenshot of *MUSE* in progress.

5.5 Game Platform

MUSE is a one page, proof-of-concept web application running in the *Chrome* web browser. We chose to develop for the web platform for portability. Although browser based, *MUSE* is designed for co-located play. Co-location of users in collaborative games significantly improves the overall perceived quality of gameplay [20-22], therefore *MUSE* was designed for up to four players sharing one

screen display. Players use game pad controllers as input devices (we tested *MUSE* with both wireless gamepads - *Logitech F710* - and wired ones - *XBOX one*). The real-time, audio processing of *MUSE* is built using the Web Audio API (application programming interface), a high-level JavaScript API for processing and synthesizing audio in web applications [23]. The application is controlled through game pad controllers, currently supported in some web browsers through the Gamepad API [24].

6. PLAY TESTING

Fourteen participants tested *MUSE* during an open gallery exhibition at the University of Calgary. On several occasions two-player groups played the game, with each player controlling two musical *BLOCKS* while on two occasions a complete group of four-players joined a game session. The system setup consisted in one laptop running *MUSE* in the *Chrome* web browser with four *Logitech F710* wireless controllers connected to it. Players were seated on stools positioned around a small coffee table. The visuals were projected on the wall surface using a short-throw projector placed under the table. The audio output was played through two loud speakers positioned to the left and right of the projected image. A gameplay video recording of a one-player game session of *MUSE* is available online [25].

6.1 Observations and Reflections

6.1.1 Game as Sense-Pleasure

None of the users expressed aural discomfort during any of the most extreme *BLOCKS*' configurations on the grid. Due to the timed turn taking, players could quickly change the music output if they considered it less than satisfactory. Moreover, we observed some participants nodding their head or tapping their feet to the beat. By not giving users access to individual pitch or velocity controls, we found the proposed "no-wrong-notes" environment leading to an overall "pleasant musical output" to be effective. Many of the participants expressed their satisfaction with *MUSE* as being "really fun" or "awesome" while some even expressed their desire to come back and play it again.

6.1.2 Game as Self-Expression

Although players had the liberty to perform any action they wished on their turn, the ever-going, continuous sound output provided them with a musical context to which they either contributed further, abruptly changed or erased it almost completely. We noticed that soon after getting familiar with the interface, some players started making game choices of a more interesting musical quality within the given mood and characteristics of the music output at the time of their turn. We believe that our design approach allows creative self-expression to migrate from being an isolated, independent action to becoming a fundamental component of a unified, collaborative experience.

Players in two-player groups (controlling two loops each) became more interested in organizing the *BLOCKS*

into a particular configuration of shapes/positions in order to produce a pre-conceived musical result. This finding suggests that one-to-many actions – similar to the *Swap Blocks* action where a single press of a button is needed to arrange several players in a different configuration – would strongly appeal to users with an interest in musical arranging.

Some players found that using the *Move Block* action repeatedly on their own *BLOCK* in combination with continuously changing its shape led to a very rewarding “solo” experience. They expressed disappointment however, when by accident they moved onto a passive player’s tile, thus removing that player from the grid and silencing it, which resulted in losing the harmonic support that inspired them to perform the solo in the first place. It seemed obvious to us the need to implement a “solo” mode in which the removal mechanic of the passive player is disabled. We are also considering making use of the two 2-axis analog joysticks as expressive controls mapped to several musical or sound parameters in the future.

Although players reported having a good experience with *MUSE* and were observed feeling in control of their musical contributions for most of the time, we feel that the level of long-term engagement and replay value of *MUSE* is still not as high as we would like it to be and needs to be addressed in the future. As mentioned before, the main reason why musical instruments offer long-term engagement to their users is the opportunity for skill mastery [26]. With that understanding in mind, we are looking at ways in which we can provide users with ways of improving their musical skill in *MUSE* without compromising the “ease-of-use” that characterizes most *musical toys*. We elaborate more on this insight in section 6.1.6.

6.1.3 Game as Submission (pastime)

The implementation of the turn-taking mechanic together with that of limited turn action time confirmed our expectations regarding the impact this will have on the flow of the game: players were more attentive to their choice of action and looking forward to their next turn. On subsequent turns, some players went back to the action they were previously performing while others explored the game’s options further. While waiting for their turn, passive players keenly observed and listened to the musical changes performed by the active player, this essentially building up their excitement in anticipation of their own turn [13].

6.1.4 Game as Discovery

Since the tutorial does not mention the gameplay mechanic of temporarily silencing and removing other players from the game by moving onto their tiles, players were pleasantly surprised to discover this feature by themselves. Subsequently, this game mechanic got used progressively more. Since there is no other gameplay purpose for removing a player other than a pure musical one, players made use of this mechanic rather creatively. This led us to consider implementing more “hidden” musical/gameplay features in *MUSE* in the future and make this “surprise” component known to players early in the game. We anticipate

that adding events and controls of uncertain quality but with a definite chance of occurring at a later time in the game, will keep the players’ engagement and excitement levels high for longer periods of play time.

6.1.5 Game as Fellowship

Players who knew each other before playing the game, tended to discuss the game’s controls and features more than players who never met before. The interaction at communication level, also noted in other games’ play testing sessions [27], makes for an overall relaxed atmosphere and adds to the enjoyment of the participants when playing the game [20]. Future features of *MUSE* taking advantage of this knowledge may include short real-time challenges where participants have to actually work together towards a common musical goal, thus addressing one of the secondary dynamics discussed earlier, that of *Fellowship*.

6.1.6 Game as Challenge

One of the approaches to long-term engagement we strongly consider implementing in the future, is the design of two distinct, main game modes: a basic or *learner* mode, and an advanced or *performer* mode. The *learner* mode could use a level-design approach (usually found in computer games) that gradually increases in complexity as the player progresses through the game levels. Users would have to master the set of musical concepts and controls of a given game level before being allowed access to higher levels. Moreover, their learning progress during the *learner* mode could be saved in player profiles within the game. When playing in *performer* mode, players would load their profiles and have instant access to any game skills / controls they managed to learn so far. Having players with higher skill levels playing together with less advanced users while in *performer* mode, may encourage the latter ones to master the basics faster in order to gain access to the more expressive musical features and controls showcased by advanced players.

7. CONCLUSION

The initial overall positive user feedback gave us confidence in our design approach to creating a collaborative, real-time music-making sandbox environment. Nevertheless, further formal testing such as usability studies and rigorous playtests are required to gather the data needed to clearly establish the design approaches most suitable for developing real-time collaborative music interfaces for broad audiences. Based on our informal evaluations we believe that our design approach considerably fulfilled our proposed proof-of-concept expectations.

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8. REFERENCES

- [1] K. Miller, "Schizophonic Performance: Guitar Hero, Rock Band, and Virtual Virtuosity," *Journal of the Society for American Music*, vol. 3, pp. 395-429, 11, 2009.
- [2] M. Kalinauskas, "Gamification in fostering creativity," *Social Technologies*, pp. 62-75, 2014.
- [3] A. Xambó, R. Laney, and C. Dobbyn, "TOUCHtr4ck: Democratic collaborative music," in *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Tangible, Embedded, and Embodied Interaction*, 2011, pp. 309-312.
- [4] C. Ning and S. Zhou, "The music pattern: A creative tabletop music creation platform," *Computers in Entertainment (CIE)*, vol. 8, pp. 13, 2010.
- [5] M. D. Thibeault, "The Power of Limits and the Pleasure of Games: An Easy and Fun Piano Duo Improvisation," *General Music Today*, vol. 25, pp. 50-53, 2012.
- [6] S. Jordà, "The reactable: Tangible and tabletop music performance," in *CHI'10 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2010, pp. 2989-2994.
- [7] J. J. Gibson, "The theory of affordances," *Hilldale, USA*, 1977.
- [8] R. Caillois, *Man, Play and Games*. Free Press, 1961.
- [9] J. Juul, "The open and the closed: Games of emergence and games of progression." in *CGDC Conf.* 2002.
- [10] S. Deterding, D. Dixon, R. Khaled, and L. Nacke, "From game design elements to gamefulness: Defining gamification," in *Proceedings of the 15th International Academic MindTrek Conference: Envisioning Future Media Environments*, Tampere, Finland, 2011, pp. 9-15.
- [11] B. Brathwaite and I. Schreiber, *Challenges for Game Designers*. Rockland, MA, USA: Charles River Media Inc., 2008.
- [12] P. Zhang, "Technical Opinion: Motivational Affordances: Reasons for ICT Design and Use," *Communications ACM*, vol. 51, pp. 145-147, 2008.
- [13] S. Deterding, "Situated motivational affordances of game elements: A conceptual model," in *Gamification: Using Game Design Elements in Non-Gaming Contexts, a Workshop at CHI*, 2011.
- [14] M. Csikszentmihalyi, *Flow: The Psychology of Optimal Experience*. Harper & Row, 1990.
- [15] R. Hunicke, M. LeBlanc, and R. Zubek, "MDA: A formal approach to game design and game research," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Workshop on Challenges in Game AI*, 2004.
- [16] J. W. Bernard, "The minimalist aesthetic in the plastic arts and in music," *Perspectives of New Music*, pp. 86-132, 1993.
- [17] B. Bengler and N. Bryan-Kinns, "Designing collaborative musical experiences for broad audiences," in *Proceedings of the Ninth ACM Conference on Creativity & Cognition*, 2013, pp.234-242.
- [18] (April 22, 2015). *AJAX: Asynchronous JavaScript and XML*. Available: https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/AJAX/Getting_Started.
- [19] R. Paradise and B. Rogoff, "Side by side: Learning by observing and pitching in," *Ethos*, vol. 37, pp. 102-138, 2009.
- [20] E. Jakobs, A. H. Fischer, and A. S. Manstead, "Emotional experience as a function of social context: The role of the other," *J. Nonverbal Behav.*, vol. 21, pp. 103-130, 1997.
- [21] Y. A. De Kort and W. A. Ijsselsteijn, "People, places, and play: player experience in a socio-spatial context," *Computers in Entertainment (CIE)*, vol. 6, pp. 18, 2008.
- [22] B. H. Thomas, "The Future of Entertainment: How Play and Engaging Experience Can Contribute to the Society," *Computer Entertainment*, vol. 8, pp. 22:1-22:3, 2010.
- [23] (April 22, 2015). *Web Audio API*. Available: https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/API/Web_Audio_API.
- [24] (April 22, 2015). *Gamepad API*. Available: <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/Guide/API/Gamepad>.
- [25] "MUSE gameplay (a Music Sandbox Experience for collaborative play in real time)," *YouTube*. n.d. [Online] Available: http://youtu.be/ySg728q_bwA [June 17, 2015].
- [26] S. Holland, K. Wilkie, P. Mulholland and A. Seago, *Music and Human-Computer Interaction*. Springer, 2013.
- [27] K. Isbister and N. Schaffer, *Game Usability: Advancing the Player Experience*. CRC Press, 2008.